

A Study to Determine the Emotional and Behavioral Problems Among Children of Employed Mother's in Selected Schools at Vijayapur District Karnataka

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Abstract:- A descriptive design was used in this study. It describes the phenomena in real life situation. It provides accurate account of the characteristics of particular individuals, and situation of groups. The samples consist of 100 children of employed mothers who fulfill the inclusion criteria are selected. Convenience sampling technique was used in this study. Two schools were selected. Before the data collection, the researcher got the formal permission from the principal of Oxfordschool at Vijayapur District Karnataka. The total numbers of students were 450; the survey was conducted among the students to find out the children of employed mother. The total numbers of employed mothers were 55. In Excellent Higher Secondary School the total number of students were approximately 750, the survey was conducted among the students to find out the children of employed mothers. The total number of employed mothers are 123 in that 45 students were selected as sample of those who fulfill the inclusion criteria.

➤ **Objectives:**

- To assess the emotional problems among children of employed mothers in selected schools.
- To assess the behavioral problems among children of employed mothers in selected school
- To find out the correlation between emotional and behavioral problems of children of employed mothers
- To find out the association between the emotional problems of children of employed mothers and selected demographic variables such as age of children, sex of children, education of mothers, family income, mother's religion, occupation, working hours, type of family, number of siblings, parental status, recreational facilities and child's hobbies, type of school and educational system.

- To find out the association between the behavioral problems of children of employed mothers and selected demographic

➤ **Assumption**

- Children of employed mothers will have more emotional and behavioral problems than children of unemployed mothers.
- Selected demographic variables may influence the emotional and behavioral problems of children

➤ **Major Findings of the Study:**

- In emotional problems, 29% of children had severe emotional problems, 49% of them had moderate emotional problems, and 22% of them had mild emotional problems.
- In behavioral problems, 21% of children had severe behavioral problems, 45% had moderate level of behavioral problems, and 34% of them had mild behavioral problems.
- There is a significant positive correlation between emotional and behavioral problems among children of employed mothers.
- There is a significant association between emotional problems and selected demographic variables such as education of the mother, family income, and mother's occupation, working hours, number of siblings, family status, recreational facilities, and educational system.
- There is a significant association between behavioral problems and selected demographic variables such as education of the mother, family income, mother's occupation, working hours, type of family, number of siblings, family status, recreational facilities, child hobbies, type of school, and educational system.

➤ *Conclusion*

Childhood is the period of paramount importance in life. During childhood, the child undergoes a remarkable transformation from a helpless dependent infant to an independent self-sufficient individual with his own views. From the above study, the investigator would like to conclude that the majority of the children among employed mothers were having moderate to severe emotional and behavioral problems.

The parents must realize their parental role in order to help and guide the children to lead their life in a healthy manner both physically and mentally. Mothers can spend as much time as possible to express their feelings and thoughts and make time qualitative and memorable by taking them out, help those with their homework and enquiring about their days spend at school. The time should be spent with the children by the parents irrespective of their profession will help to reduce the behavioral and emotional problems.

Keywords:- Emotional ,Behavioral ,Problems, Children ,Employed Mother.

I. INTRUCTION

Children are the inheritance from God. They are like clay in the potter's hand. Handled with love and care, they become something beautiful or else they will break. Children are developing individuals whose capacities and coping skills change markedly during childhood. The childhood is the period of life characterized by change, challenge, and the necessity for adoption. During the childhood, the child undergoes a remarkable transformation from a helpless dependent infant to an independent self-sufficient individual with his own views and outlook capable of embarking on a carrier and living separate from his family.

Childhood is the period of dependence; gradually children learn to adjust in the environment. However, when there is any complexity around them they cannot adjust in the circumstances. Then they become unable to behave socially acceptable way and behavioral problem develop with them. The psychological disturbance in childhood is usually defined as an abnormality in at least one of these three areas-emotion, behavior, and relationship.

The emotional needs are considered as emotional food for healthy behavior. The children are dependent on their parents, so parents are responsible for the fulfillment of the emotional needs. The most common sign of the emotional problem ranges from phobia to school refusal, Separation anxiety, withdrawn from peer group, easily frustrated, demands must be met immediately, nightmares, cries often and easily, attention deficit, mood changing which are prevalence during childhood.

Von Ammon (2000) described that emotional problems range from anxiety, phobia to school refusal, more that are prevalence in the age group of 10-16 yrs.

Every child should have tender loving care and sense of security about protection from parents and family. They should have opportunity for development of independence, trust, confidence and self-respect. There should be adequate social and emotional interaction with discipline. The child should get scope for self-expression and recreation. Parents should be aware about achievements of their children and express acceptance of positive attitude.

Behavioral problems commonly occur during childhood. Major behavioral problems are the significant deviation from socially accepted normal behavior. Behavioral problems always require special attention. It is defined as behavior, thought, or feelings differ quantitatively from the norm and as the result of this, differences the child is either suffering significantly or development are being significantly impaired. **(DavidCottrell 2000)**

Numerous behaviors are considered appropriate at certain early development. Levels are obviously pathogenic when they present at later age. These behaviors are probably the results of frustration and anger. These abnormal behaviors will create problems not only for themselves but for others also. Behavioral problems commonly during childhood are Learning difficulties, Short attention span, Bed wetting, Refuse to talk, Becoming aggressive, Steal at home, Lying and cheating, Breaking the property, Temper tantrum, Thump sucking, Nail biting, Sleep disorder, etc.

Saramma (1999) assessed the behavioral problems faced by the school-going children of employed mothers. The objective of the study was to identify the behavioral problems with regard to separation of parents. The research finding showed that the mean score in behavioral problem was 45.5 and 30% of the schoolchildren are having behavioral problem.

➤ *Need for The Study*

Everyone loves children and wishes them to be in well mannered, well behaved and they should work and study to achieve their desired goals and fulfill their parent's dreams, but some amount of behavioral problems occur among children in the age group of 6-12 years. This psychological disturbance in childhood is usually defined as an abnormality in one of these three areas emotion, behavior and relationship.

Mental health surveys are important for the planning of mental health services for children, which aim to prevent, detect and treat childhood psychiatric morbidity, to promote normal development and enable young people to reach their full potentiality. Early epidemiological surveys in various countries have yielded prevalence estimates of childhood mental health problems, which ranged widely between 5% and 26% depending on the survey instrument used. More recent studies using DSM IV (Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders) criteria and structured clinical interview for diagnosis yielded rates between 9% and 16%.

Assessing emotional and behavioral problems in children can be difficult. Research has shown that children often reports higher levels of depression than the adults rating and that adults do not always know enough about Childs feelings and state of mind.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

A Study To Determine The Emotional And Behavioral Problems Among Children Of Employed Mother's In Selected Schools At Vijayapur District Karnataka.

A. *Assumptions*

This study assumes that:

Children of employed mother's will have more emotional and behavioral problem than children of unemployed mothers. Selected demographic variables may influence the emotional and behavioral problems of children.

➤ *Hypotheses*

The study is based on the following hypothesis and this will be tested at 0.05 levels of significance

• *H1:*

There will be a correlation between emotional and behavioral problems among children of employed mothers.

• *H2:*

There will be a significant association between emotional problems among children of employed mothers and selected demographic variables such as age, sex, and education of mothers, family income, mother's religion, and occupation, working hours, type of family, number of siblings, parental status, recreational facilities and child's hobbies, type of school and educational system.

• *H3:*

There will be a significant association between behavioral problems among children of employed mothers and selected demographic variables

B. *Research Approach:*

Quantitative research approach was adopted in this study. The purpose of the study is to assess the behavioral and emotional problems among children of employed mothers in selected schools, at Vijayapur District Karnataka, Sivagangai, Tamil Nadu, India.

III. RESEARCH DESIGN

A **descriptive design** was used in this study. It describes the phenomena in real life situation. It provides accurate account of the characteristics of particular individuals, and situation of groups.

➤ *Setting Of The Study:*

The setting of the study was in selected schools at Vijayapur District Karnataka. The schools selected were Oxford middle School, in Vijayapur District Karnataka. It situated 2kms away from Bustand. The total strength of the school was approximately 450, among that 55 students have employed mothers, for the study purpose the researcher selected 55 samples of those who fulfill the inclusion criteria.

The Excellent Higher Secondary School, Vijayapur District Karnataka with the total strength of approximately 750 comprising of about 250 students who were in the age between 6-12years. Among them, 123 children have employed mothers. Forty-five samples were selected from those who fulfill the inclusion criteria. This School is situated 2kms away from Bustand.

➤ *Population*

The target population of the study was children between the age group of 6-12years and those who are studying in excellent Higher Secondary School, and Oxford middle School at Vijayapur District Karnataka.

➤ *Sample*

The samples consist of children those who are in the age group between 6-12years.

➤ *Sample Size*

The samples consist of 100 children of employed mothers whofulfill the inclusion criteria are selected.

➤ *Sampling Technique:*

Convenience sampling technique was used in this study. Two schools were selected. Before the data collection, the researcher got the formal permission from the principal of Oxford school at Vijayapur District Karnataka.

➤ *Criteria for Sample Selection*

The following were the inclusive and exclusive criteria for the selection of the samples.

➤ *Inclusion Criteria*

- *Children of employed mothers are included.*
- *Both male and female children of employed mothers.*
- *Children between the age group of 6-12 years.*
- *Children studying in selected schools.*
- *Children who are willing to participate in this study*

➤ *Exclusion Criteria*

- *Children of housewife were excluded.*
- *Children who are not willing to participate are excluded.*
- *Children with long term illness*

➤ *Selection of the Tool:*

An Achenbach's modified child behavior checklist was used to assess the behavioral problems and Modified Conner's Abbreviated Rating Scale was used to assess the emotional problems among children of employed mothers. The selected tools were printed in both Kannada and English.

➤ *Plan for Data Analysis:*

Data were analyzed based on the objectives. Frequency and Percentages were computed for describing the sample characteristics. Correlation was used to find out the relation between emotional and behavioral problems. Chi square was used to find out the association between emotional and behavioral problems among children of employed mothers and demographic variable such as age, sex, education of mothers, family income, mothers religion, occupation, working hours, type of family, number of siblings, parental status, recreational facilities and child's hobbies, type of school, educational system.

IV. RESULTS

A. *Section: I*

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Samples According to their Selected Demographic Variables.

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Samples According to their Selected Demographic Variables (N = 100)

S. No	Demographic variables	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age of the children		
	6-7 years	23	23
	8-10 years	46	46
2.	Sex of the child		
	Male	58	58
	Female	42	42
3.	Educational of the mother		
	Illiterate	3	3
	Primary	51	51
	Secondary	22	22
4.	Family income		
	Below 5000/- month	26	26
	5001 to 10000/- month	42	42
	Above 10001/- month	32	32
5.	Mothers Religion		
	Hindu	32	32
	Christian	53	53
6.	Mother's Occupation		
	Government employer	30	30
	Non government employer	54	54
7.	Working hours		
	6 hours	20	20
	8 hours	51	51
8.	Type of family		
	Joint family	31	31
	Nuclear family	62	62
9.	Number of Siblings)		
	1child	49	49
	2children	47	47
	3children	4	4
10.	Family Status		
	Organized	96	96
	Disorganized	4	4
11.	Recreational facilities		

	TV	73	73
	Radio	1	1
	Computer	24	24
	Video game	2	2
12.	Child hobbies		
	Watching TV	46	46
	Stamp Collection(C)	6	6
	Playing	43	43
	Others	5	5
13.	Type of School		
	Government School	45	45
	Private School	46	46
	Matriculation	9	9
14.	Educational System		
	State Board	83	83
	Central Board	17	17

➤ Frequency Distribution of Samples Interm of Sex of the Child

Fig 1 Frequency Distribution of Samples Interm of Sex of the Child

➤ Frequency Distribution of Samples Interm of Education of the Mothers

Fig 2 Frequency Distribution of Samples Interm of Education of the Mothers

B. Section II

Distribution of Behavioral Problems Among Children of Employed Mothers.

Table 2 Distribution of Behavioral Problems Among Children of Employed Mothers (n = 100)

S. No	Level of Behavioral problems	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
1	Severe Behavioral problems	21	21
2.	Moderate behavioral Problems	45	45
3.	Mild Behavioral problems	34	34

Shows that the majority of subjects 45 (45%) had moderate level of behavioral problems 34 (34%) of them had mild behavioral problems and 21 (21%) of the subjects were having severe behavioral problems.

C. Section: III

Distribution of Level of Emotional Problems Among Children of Employed Mother’s.

Table 3 Distribution of Level of Emotional Problems Among Children of Employed Mother’s (n = 100)

S. No	Level of Emotional problems	Frequencies (F)	Percentage (%)
1.	Severe Emotional Problems	29	29
2.	Moderate Emotional Problems	49	49
3.	Mild Emotional Problems	22	22

The Majority of subjects 49 (49%) were having moderate level of emotional problems, 29 (29%) of them were having severe level of emotional problems and 22 (22%) of subjects were having wild emotional problems.

D. Section IV

Relationship between Behavioral and Emotional Problems Among Children of Employed Mothers.

Table 4 Relationship between Behavioral and Emotional Problems Among Children of Employed Mothers

Particular	Correlation ‘r ‘	Statistical result
Behavioral Problems vs Emotional Problems	0.817	Positive correlation

The above table indicates that there is a positive correlation between behavioral and emotional problems among children of employed mothers (r = 0.817).

To find out the relationship between behavioral and emotional problems correlation was used. The computed ‘r’ value is + 0.817 The positive correlation was found between Behavioral and emotional Problem.

E. Section V

Association between Emotional Problems and Selected Demographic Variables Among Children of Employed Mothers.

Table 5 Association between Emotional Problems and Selected Demographic Variables Among Children of Employed Mothers (N=100)

S. No	Demographic variables	Severe level emotional problem	Moderate level emotional problem	Mild emotional problem	χ^2
1.	Age of the Children 6-7 years 8-10 years 11-12 years	5 6 7	5 34 18	3 6 6	#2.438
2.	Sex of the Child Male Female	10 8	40 27	8 7	#0.315
3.	Educational of the Mother Illiterate Primary Secondary Graduate	1 8 5 4	2 36 16 13	0 7 1 7	*11.912
4.	Family income Below 5000/- month 5001 to 10000/- month Above 10001/- month	4 11 3	18 29 20	4 2 9	*12.298

5.	Mothers Religion Hindu Christian Muslim	6 8 4	22 37 8	4 8 3	#2.072
6.	Mother's Occupation Government employer Non Government Employer Self Employer	7 8 3	20 37 10	3 9 3	*11.858
7.	Working Hours 6 Hours 8 Hours 12 Hours and Above	5 8 3	14 30 23	1 11 3	*6.045
8.	Type of family Joint family Nuclear family Extended family	8 8 2	20 43 4	3 11 1	#5.832
9.	Number of Siblings 1 2 3 4 and above	8 9 1 0	33 31 3 0	8 7 0 0	*20.248
10.	Family Status Organized Disorganized	15 2	66 2	15 0	*16.94
11.	Recreational fealties TV Radio Computer Video game	14 0 3 1	50 1 15 1	9 0 6 0	#12.93
12.	Child hobbies watching TV stamp collection playing others	11 1 5 1	30 3 30 4	5 2 8 0	#5.537
13.	Type of School Government school Private school Matriculation	11 6 1	30 31 6	4 9 2	#3.952
14.	Educational System State board Central board	18 0	52 15	13 2	*6.178

* Significant # Not Significant

Table 5 shows the association between emotional and demographic variables among children of employed mothers. The result shows that the calculated value for emotional problem and demographic variables such as age of the children, mother's education, family income, mother's religion, occupation, working hours, type of family, number of siblings, family status, recreational facilities, child hobbies, type of school, educational system is greater than the table value.

➤ *Nursing Practice:*

Schoolchildren who are the citizen of tomorrow should have sound mind, body, and soul. The physical health is depending on the mental health. So it is the responsibility of the nurse to teach the employed mother regarding preventive measures to tackle the emotional and behavioral problems, and advice the mother to maintain a loving stable relationship between the parents and children. Nurse can

provide teaching to the mother during the prenatal period how to care the child to prevent emotional and behavioral problems.

➤ *Nursing Education:*

Education helps the individual to learn new things and there by plays an important role in changing behavior of the learner. Therefore, nurses need to equip themselves with knowledge regarding behavioral and emotional problems in that way they will be able to impart the knowledge to the children. Nurses at postgraduate level creating awareness about psychosocial disturbances may lead to behavioral problems during developmental stages. Provide counseling services for children and their parents to solve the problems through tender loving care for children.

➤ *Nursing Administration:*

The nurse administrator should plan to organize in-service education programme for nursing personnel regarding assessment of behavioral and emotional problems and making them aware about the causes of behavioral problems to the mother. So that, it will be helpful to them to impart knowledge to children. Nurse administrator should motivate nursing personnel to participate, conduct counseling program, and conduct schoolcamp for early detection and treatment of behavioral and emotional problems of children.

➤ *Nursing Research:*

The result of the present study shows that the emotional and behavioral problems among children of employed mothers are more common. Researchers should focus on behavior modification of children after giving guidance to mothers. Nurse researcher should also conduct the research and provide health education for the benefit of schoolchildren at their primary school level. Therefore, that it will be helpful for them in later years.

V. RECOMMENDATION

➤ *Based on the findings of the study it is recommended that*

- A similar study may be replicated on large samples with different demographic variables.
- A comparative study can be conducted to find the prevalence of emotional and behavioral problems among rural and urban schoolchildren.
- A study may be conducted to identify the effectiveness of structured teaching programme in modification of children's behavior.
- A comparative study can be conducted to find out the emotional and behavioral problems among children of employed and non-employed mothers.
- A study can be conducted to find out the effectiveness of counseling programme to modify the behavioral and emotional problems among children of employed mothers.

VI. CONCLUSION

The parents must realize their parental role in order to help and guide the children to lead their life in a healthy manner both physically and mentally. Mothers can spend as much time as possible to express their feelings and thoughts and make time qualitative and memorable by taking them out, help those with their homework and enquiring about their days spend at school. The time should be spent with the children by the parents irrespective of their profession will help to reduce the behavioral and emotional problems.

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